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“SATISFACTION INDEX ANALYSIS OF MANGALWEDHA TOURIST CENTRE IN SOLAPUR DISTRICT (MS)”

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ABSTRACT :-

Tourism comprises the activities of persons traveling and staying in outside places from their usual environment. It becomes a main contributor to country revenues it is important to review the problem aroused in the strategic concept of marketing one city. Tourist always visit a particular place in search of pleasure. Some times this motive is supplemented by other motives like business, education, religious, medical, friends and relatives etc. As like hotels, transport the tourism is fastest growing industries. Mangalwedha tourist center

is selected for the analysis of tourism attractions and tourist satisfaction. For these 200 pilgrims or tourists are selected during the whole one year (2018). They selected on the basis of spot visiting persons in different times. To giving the priority of eleven factors for analysis tourism development calculated the satisfaction index. Among the facilities transport and darshan are good. But the spot guidance, clean and Hygienic premises, doctorate facilities in temple and primary basic facilities are lowest satisfactory.

Keywords: Leisure, Cultural Heritage, Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION:

Tourism is travel for recreational leisure or business purposes and it is temporary movement of people at a place outside their normal place of work or residence. Tourist always visit a particular place in search of pleasure. Some times this motive is supplemented by other motives like business, education, religious, medical, friends and relatives etc. As like hotels, transport the tourism is fastest growing industries. Encouragement of tourism may be necessary for promoting national integration and awareness of rich cultural heritage.

Mangalwedha is very important tourism place in Solapur district which has got natural heritage. Some tourist places in Solapur district as well as Mangalwedha tahsil are neglected which can be developed for tourism. Many tourists visited at this place from different parts of India. But they face problems like food and drinking water, accommodation, parking facility etc. So it is need to develop for tourist satisfaction purpose.

Study Region:

Mangalwedha city is one of the western most city in Solapur district. It is situated between latitude of 17°31'43"E to 17°32'25"E and longitude of 75°25'53" N to 75°27'47"N. The city situated 458m mean sea level. Mangalwedha city situated 55km west of the district headquarters at Solapur and 25km south west of Pandharpur. Due to rich black soil, it is also popular for maldandijawor production in Maharashtra. It is also called the JaworicheKothar in Solapur district.

Objectives: Some specific objectives of the study are as follows-

1. To asses the satisfaction of tourists who visits of the Mangalwedha.
2. To find out the miss management and facility provided for tourists in Mangalwedha.

Database and Methodology:

Present analysis is based upon data collection, observation and information given by tourist come out from direct observation and also from information resources. The data collected through field survey questionnaire. With the help of questionnaire researcher interviewed 200 tourist Mangalwedha. The data observed convert into numerical value for 8 to 10 for excellent, 6 to 7 for good, 4 to 5 for satisfaction and 1 to 3 for unsatisfied.

Where they obtained values used for calculating satisfaction index using following formula.

$$SLi = \frac{\sum Mi \times Ni}{N}$$

Where,

Sli = satisfaction index for 'i' factor

Mi = Numerical value for particular level of satisfaction for the I factor

Ni = No. of respondent driving the particular level of satisfaction for the i factor.

N=Total no of respondents for that factor for all level of satisfaction.

Discussions:

Mangalwedha is called the land of saints, as saint Damaji, saint Chokhamela are from Mangalwedha. In the 14th century, Mangalwedha was an active workplace of many saints such as saint Damaji, saint Chokhamela, saint Gadgebaba, saint Gopabai, saint Kanhopatra, shri Swami Samarth, shriSitaramMaharaj and other.

Damajipant was a great saint who was working and living at Mangalwedha near Solapur in Maharashtra. He used to work for the muslim king of Bidar by maintaining the stock of grains in the godown at Mangalwedha. He was very pious, kind hearted and immersed in Harichintana. His wife was equally cooperative and devoted. Once there was a great famine in that region and people, cattle died of starvation. On one afternoon, there came a brahmin at Damajipant's door at lunchtime. Damajipant invited him to take food with him and other guests. While eating, the brahmin started to cry. When asked the reason of his sorrow, he told that his family was starving at Pandharpur, but he was eating heartlessly. Damajipant assured him that he would get lot of grains to take for his family. After lunch, he was given 2 khandi rice, which was loaded in the bullock cart to be taken to Pandharpur.

On the way to Pandharpur, many starving poor people attacked the brahmin and took away his rice. When they learnt that, the brahmin had received the grains from Damajipant at Mangalwedha, a huge crowd came to Damajipant and piteously requested for grains. His wife too suggested that the poor and starving people should be helped.

There was only one solution. Damajipant opened the godown of muslim king and distributed the grains freely to everyone. Soon the news spread that, Damajipant was distributing the grains and a lot of people from the areas affected by famine came. All of them received grains freely. Though all of them praised Damajipant to the skies, he remained humble. However, there was one Kannada clerk working for the same king at Mangalwedha, who was jealous of Damajipant. He immediately went to Bidar and informed

the king that his godown was emptied by Damajipant without informing him. The king was enraged and ordered capturing of Damajipant. The soldiers arrived at Damajipant door and showed him king's order. Damajipant was unmoved, but requested them to take him to Bidar via Pandharpur. The soldiers agreed and they arrived at Pandharpur. Damajipant took bath in the river Chandrabhaga and went to see Lord Vitthala. There, he intently looked at the Lord and told him, that, that was the last he could be seeing Him. Tears came to eyes of Damajipant. Soldiers took him away and they started towards Bidar.

Lord Vitthala, immediately disguised as VithooMahar came to the king of Bidar carrying a huge load on His back. He showed a letter written in the handwriting of Damajipant to the guards who let Him in. There VithooMahar entered the Durbar of the king and offered him the salutations. He introduced Himself as the servant of Damajipant and told the king that, there was a great deficiency of grains all over Mangalwedha and the adjoining areas due to famine and that Damajipant had sold all the grains for a very high price. He gave the huge bag of gold coins to the king and the letter written in Damajipant's handwriting to the king and requested him to issue a receipt for the same. The king was astonished and immediately asked his treasury people to count the money. The money was uncountable and was in several lakhs. The king was extremely happy and felt ashamed about his wrong decision to arrest Damajipant based on a false complaint. He thanked VithooMahar, issued a receipt to Him and also presented ornaments, a horse and an elephant and rich clothes to be handed over to Damajipant. VithooMahar took everything and went to Mangalwedha and showed it to the family of Damajipant and disappeared. However, since, Damajipant was going to Bidar via Pandharpur he did not know anything. Sometime after the departure of VithooMahar, Damajipant entered Durbar and offered his salutations to the king. The king was surprised to see him again. The king came to Damajipant and hugged him with great affection and offered his apologies for his mistake. Damajipant was bewildered and looked at the king disbelievingly. Then the king told him how he had just received the money earned by Damajipant by selling the grains and so on. The king also described in minute details, the name and other features of Damajipant's faithful servant. Damajipant immediately understood that it was the Lord of Pandharpur, who had done everything for his devotee. When tears started to roll down his cheeks, the king was surprised. Damajipant explained everything to him and told the king, that he was resigning his job, as the Lord had work for him and he did not want to trouble again. The king was surprised and praised Damajipant for his devotion. Damajipant returned to Mangalwedha and found all the gifts and the receipt at his home and told everything that had happened. He donated everything to the poor people and went to Pandharpur. He served the Lord at Pandharpur till the very end. Even now there is a temple in the memory of Damajipant at Mangalwedha.

Chokhamelaor Chokhoba was a 14th century saint poet. He was a varkari. There is a very little recorded history of Chokhamela's life. Chokha belonged to the cast of untouchables. At that time untouchables were not a part of social fold. They were neglected. They were thought to be impure. They were expected to live off on the leftovers given by the upper-castes. They were denied education. They were even forbidden to enter the temple. All these things are reflected in Chokhamela's poetry. He was contemporary saint-poet of Jnyaneshwar, the late 13th century poet-saint and philosopher. Namdev was another contemporary saint. He had a great influence on Chokhamela. Chokha considered him as his Guru. It is said that this great saint-poet died with other laborers when the part of the fort they were helping to build, collapsed on them. There is also a popular legend that Chokhamela's friend as well as Guru went to find his remains and picked up those bones which murmur "VitthalVitthal" The bones were buried outside the gate of main temple of Vithoba in Pandharpur. And a shrine is built there. The Varkaris and devotees take the darshan of this shrine. There is also one beautiful shrine built at the place where he died in Mangalwedha.

Kanhopatra (15th century) is a female Hindu Varkari poet-saint. Kanhopatra wrote Marathi abhanga compositions, which deal with her devotion to Vithoba, the patron deity of the Varkaris and her struggle to balance this with her profession. Not much is known about the historical Kanhopatra's life. Much of the legends that deal with her life concentrate upon her death when she chose to surrender to Vithoba rather

become a concubine of the king of Bedar. Kanhopatra was a daughter of a courtesan named Shyama, who lived in the town of Mangalwedha. Kanhopatra was forced in the courtesans's life, though she detested it. Later, Kanhopatra withdrew from society and lived in Pandharpur, where the chief temple of Vithoba stands. She spent rest of her life singing and wrote ovi style poems as well as abhanga poems dedicated to Vithoba. Upon hearing the tales of Kanhopatra's beauty, the king of Bedar ordered her to be his concubine. When she refused, the king sent his men to get her by force. Kanhopatra took refuge in the Vithoba temple of Pandharpur, the central shrine of god Vithoba. Kanhopatra died there in mysterious circumstances. Though legend says Kanhopatra merged with the central image of Vithoba in form of marriage with Him, other theories suggest possible suicide or homicide for rebelliousness. According to legend, as per Kanhopatra's last wishes, her dead body was laid at feet of Vithoba and then buried, near the southern part of the temple. Here, a mysterious tree rose, which is worshipped by pilgrims today. Kanhopatra's dating to c. 1428 CE is related to dating to a certain Bahamani king of Bedar, who though never explicitly named in legends, is often association with Kanhopatra's legend.

Kanhopatra's abhanga frequently portray her struggle between her profession and her devotion to god Vithoba, the patron deity of the Varkaris. Only 30 of her abhanga or ovis survive today. Twenty verses of her poems are included in the anthology of Varkari saints called Sakalsant-gatha. Kanhopatra speaks of her banishment from society owing to her family profession and social stature. She talks of voluptuous thoughts of others. She feels that perhaps she was beyond "scope of God's love". She acknowledges her God as the saviour of the fallen and tells him to save her too:

O Narayana (a name of god Vishnu, who is identified with Vithoba), I lack loving faithmy nature and actions are vile. Fallen Kanhopatra offers herself to your feet, a challenge to your claims of mercy.

Kanhopatra is formerly included in the list of Sants, meaning saints in Marathi. Mahipati devotes a entire chapter in his text Bhaktavijaya extolling her devotion to Vithoba. She is cited as "an example of the real downtrodden and deserving people, persons that are saved by the merciful God". Kanhopatra's life is also retold in a 1937 Marathi film written and directed by Bhalji Pendharkar as well as a popular Marathi drama both named "Kanhopatra". (Source : Wikipedia.org)

So this place of Mangalwedha is useful for saints work that's why it should be necessary to bring out the highlights of Mangalwedha and turn the mind of tourist improving the facilities.

Satisfaction Index of Tourist(Mi):

Development of any tourist place have been need of pilgrim's opinion about the facilities, at the tourist place with the help of questionnaires a sample survey was conducted and filled up 200 pilgrims in the year of 2018. Eleven important factor which influence the level of satisfaction are identify and to be seen from the table no.1. The pilgrim tourist asked to indicate the level of satisfaction as they derived in respect of each factor by stating excellent, good, satisfactory, unsatisfied.

Table No.1: Factorwise level of satisfaction in Mangalwedha (Mi)

Sr. No.	Factor	Excellent	Good	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory	Total
1	Transport	87	47	62	04	200
2	Food and drinking water	09	41	131	19	200
3	Medical facilities	16	29	138	17	200
4	Spot guidance	04	19	96	81	200
5	Cooperation of local people	21	87	79	13	200
6	Primary Basic facilities	37	48	86	29	200
7	Hotel facilities	11	32	103	54	200
8	Clean and Hygienic premises	05	18	71	106	200
9	Doctorate facilities in temple	02	13	82	103	200
10	Parking facilities	47	63	69	21	200

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11	Darshan	53	78	64	05	200
	Total	292	475	981	452	2200
	Average	26.55	43.19	89.18	40.9	200
	Percentage	13.28	21.59	44.59	20.45	100

Source: Compiled by Researcher

For these eleven factors average of each category calculated which gives the view of pilgrims about them facilities at Mangalwedha. Category wise satisfaction reveals that the facilities provided are excellent 13.28 percent, good 21.59 percent, satisfactory 44.59 percent, and unsatisfied 20.45 percent. Therefore, the level of satisfaction of the pilgrims is very high level. 20.45 percent of pilgrims told that facilities are not satisfactory.

Table No.2: Factorwise level of satisfaction average value assigned by Tourist (Ni)

Sr. No.	Factor	Numerical value			
		Excellent	Good	Satisfactory	Unsatis-factory
1	Transport	8.92	6.62	4.76	2.50
2	Food and drinking water	8.89	6.68	4.73	2.05
3	Medical facilities	9.31	6.59	4.62	2.35
4	Spot guidance	9.75	6.53	4.53	2.22
5	Cooperation of local people	8.48	6.56	4.78	2.08
6	Primary Basic facilities	8.13	6.27	4.17	1.55
7	Hotel facilities	9.46	6.41	4.55	1.87
8	Clean and Hygienic premises	8.80	6.22	4.70	1.55
9	Doctorate facilities in temple	9.00	6.31	4.45	2.26
10	Parking facilities	8.94	6.43	5.00	1.95
11	Darshan	9.19	6.74	4.66	2.4

Source: Compiled by Researcher

The tourist opinion about the factors shows in the above table no.2 and it is calculated average namely 8 to 10 for excellent, 6 to 7 for good, 4 to 5 for satisfactory, and 1 to 3 points for unsatisfied. These numerical value are used to calculate satisfaction score and satisfaction index.

Table No. 3: Factorwise Satisfaction index (point out of 10) and their rank(Sli)

Sr. No.	Factor	Satisfaction Score	Satisfaction Index	Rank
1	Transport	1392.30	6.33	1
2	Food and drinking water	1012.47	4.60	6
3	Medical facilities	1017.58	4.62	5
4	Spot guidance	777.77	3.54	10
5	Cooperation of local people	1153.46	5.24	4
6	Primary Basic facilities	1005.34	4.57	7
7	Hotel facilities	878.81	3.99	8
8	Clean and Hygienic premises	795.96	3.62	9
9	Doctorate facilities in temple	697.71	3.17	11
10	Parking facilities	1211.22	5.50	3
11	Darshan	1323.03	6.01	2

Source: Compiled by Researcher

For the calculating satisfaction index, satisfaction score values are used and as per the priority of factor the rank assigned. First satisfaction index is for transport facility as 6.33 and last satisfaction index is

for doctorate facilities in temple as 3.17. The detail information about satisfaction index and rank number is in table no.3.

Conclusion:

Mangalwedha is famous religious tourism center. Damajipant, Cokoba and Kanhopatra is motivating religious saints who tremendously working in social work and give become ideal in present situation. So the most of people visits to Mangalwedha, especially in Sharavan month. Kartik and Ashadiwari. These pilgrims or tourist face more problems. According to my investigation transport, Darshan, parking facilities are good but ther are not satisfactory for the spot guidance, Clean and hygienic premises, doctorate facilities in temple, hotel facilities and primary basic facilities. If these facilities provide by Government or agencies or committees or native people. Mangalwedha is become popular, famous tourist center in Solapur district. It gives large employment opportunity in future.

References:

1. Agrawal S.K. and Raina A.K. (2004): *"The essences of tourism development"*, Sarup and Sons, New Delhi.
2. Batra K. L. (1989): *"Problems sand Prospects of Tourism"*,Printwell Publisher, Jaipur.
3. Chawla R (2006): *"Impact of Tourism"*,Sonali Publication New Delhi, R.No.17
4. Liburd, J. (2012):*"Tourism research 2.0. Annals of Tourism Research"*, 39(2), Pp.883-907.
5. Mane C.V. (2012): *"Satisfaction index analysis of Pal Khandoba fair, Pilgrims"*,Review of Research Vol-I, Issue-XI, Pp.1-4.
6. Veer V.R. and etail (2011): *"Level of satisfaction of agro-tourist planning for Development of agri-tourist Industry in Satara district"*, Maharashtra Geographer, Vol-I, Issue-II, Pp.124-129.
7. Wikipedia.org/wiki/mangalwedha
8. www.mangalwedha.com